

EVERYFISH

D5.4 REPORT ON WORKSHOPS

INNOVATION FOR SUSTAINABLE FISHERIES

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	Lead beneficiary: The Norwegian Directorate of Fisheries		
	Prepared by: Ole Høstmark		
Approved by: Rachel Tiller, SINTEF Ocean			

Abstract

This study conducted a series of participatory workshops across Europe to gather insights from stakeholders in the fishery industry, including fishers, scientists, and fishery managers on the implementation of automated catch registration in European fisheries. The workshops, held in Norway, Denmark, Spain, and Turkey between December 2023 and December 2024, focused on knowledge sharing, problem-solving, and networking. Participants discussed economic, regulatory, social, and ecological considerations, guided by seven identified drivers: access to areas, climate change, market, quality of life, regulations, research, and technology. The main research question addressed was: "*What will enable the implementation of automated catch registration on board European fishing vessels?*" The findings, derived from recorded and analysed workshop discussions, highlight stakeholder opinions and co-created conceptual maps.

Dissemination level

PU	Public	X
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission services)	
CI	Classified information (as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC)	

Deliverable type

R	Document, report	X
DEM	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype	
DEC	Web sites, patent fillings, videos, etc.	
OTHER	Software, technical diagram, etc.	

Authorship information

Contributing partners	Norwegian Directory of Fisheries; SINTEF Ocean; DTU; AZTI; Cukurova
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EVERYFISH consortium

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The consortium members are:

	<p>SINTEF Ocean (SO) Postboks 4762 Torgard N-7465 Trondheim NORWAY www.sintef.no</p>	<p>Project Coordinator and Manager: Rachel Tiller Rachel.tiller@sintef.no</p>
	<p>Institute of Marine Research (IMR) Postboks 1870 Nordnes 5817 Bergen NORWAY www.hi.no</p>	<p>Helge Sagen Helge.sagen@hi.no</p>
	<p>DTU Aqua (DTU) Danmarks Tekniske Universitet Willemoesvej 2 9850 Hirtshals DENMARK www.dtu.dk</p>	<p>Jordan Feekings jpfe@aqua.dtu.dk</p>
<p>DIRECTORATE OF FISHERIES</p>	<p>Norwegian Directorate of Fisheries (NDF) Postboks 185 Sentrum 5804 Bergen NORWAY www.fiskeridir.no</p>	<p>Ole Høstmark Ole.hostmark@fiskeridir.no</p>
<p>MEMBER OF BASQUE RESEARCH & TECHNOLOGY ALLIANCE</p>	<p>AZTI-Tecnalia (AZTI) 48395 Sukarrieta SPAIN www.azti.es</p>	<p>Iñaki Quincoces iquincoces@azti.es</p>
	<p>Melbu Systems AS Sminessgata 3, 8445 Melbu NORWAY http://www.melbusystems.no/</p>	<p>Einar Roger Pettersen einar@melbusystems.no</p>
	<p>Çukurova University Fisheries Faculty 01330, Saricam, Adana TURKEY http://www.cu.edu.tr/Eng/Default.aspx</p>	<p>Gökhan Gökce gokhan.gokce@ymail.com</p>
<p>Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food</p>	<p>Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (ILVO) Burgemeester Van Gansberghelaan 92 box 1 9829 Merelbeke BELGIUM https://ilvo.vlaanderen.be/en</p>	<p>Els Torrelee Els.torrelee@ilvo.vlaanderen.be</p>
	<p>Wageningen University (WU) P.O. Box 9101 6700 HB Wageningen THE NETHERLANDS www.wur.nl</p>	<p>Gert Kootstra gert.kootstra@wur.nl</p>

	<p>Anchor Lab K/S (AL) Dantes Plads 1 1559 København DENMARK https://www.anchorlab.dk/</p>	<p>Mads Dueholm mads.dueholm@anchorlab.net</p>
	<p>Wageningen Research (WR) P.O. Box 9101 6700 HB Wageningen THE NETHERLANDS www.wur.nl</p>	<p>Angelo Mencarelli angelo.mencarelli@wur.nl</p>
	<p>ASSIST Software SRL (AST) 1 Tipografie Street 720043 Suceava ROMANIA https://assist-software.net/</p>	<p>Catalin Trufin catalin.trufin@assist.ro</p>
	<p>Data Fish Technology Solutions SL (DATAFISH) Bizkaiko Jaurerria Kalea 2 48370 Bermeo (Bizkaia) SPAIN https://datafishts.com/</p>	<p>Nicolás Troncoso ntroncoso@datafishts.com</p>
	<p>University of East Anglia (UEA) Norwich Research Park Norwich Norfolk, NR4 7TJ UNITED KINGDOM https://www.uea.ac.uk/</p>	<p>Michal Mackiewicz M.Mackiewicz@uea.ac.uk</p>
	<p>Cefas Pakefield Road Lowestoft Suffolk NR33 0HT UNITED KINGDOM https://www.cefas.co.uk/</p>	<p>Thomas Catchpole thomas.catchpole@cefas.co.uk</p>
	<p>The University Court of the University of St Andrews (USTAN) College Gate St Andrews KY16 9AJ SCOTLAND www.st-andrews.ac.uk</p>	<p>Mark James maj8@st-andrews.ac.uk</p>

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Executive summary

This deliverable reports on results from eight workshops held between December 2023 and December 2024 in Norway, Denmark, Spain, and Turkey, involving stakeholders representing the fishing industry, scientists, and managers. The aim was to gather expert knowledge from stakeholders to explore perspectives on implementing automated catch registration in European fisheries. Participants, selected for their expertise and involvement in catch registration, discussed economic, regulatory, social, and ecological considerations.

The workshops focused on three pillars: knowledge sharing, problem-solving, and networking. They facilitated discussions to identify solutions and alternatives and encouraged networking among participants. An internal workshop with the core research team preceded the participatory workshops to outline research questions and relevant drivers.

The main research question was: "*What will enable the implementation of automated catch registration on board European fishing vessels?*". Seven drivers were identified prior to start of workshop facilitation: access to areas, climate change, market, quality of life, regulations, research, and technology. These drivers served as conversation starters during the workshops.

Workshops were recorded and analysed, with transcripts and co-created mental maps processed to highlight stakeholder opinions.

1. Introduction

1.1. EVERYFISH HEU motivation and background

The EVERYFISH project is a close collaboration between fisheries research, academic, industry, and governance actors, as well as technology providers across the EU and other European countries. These technological innovations will enable the fisheries sector to optimise automatic data collection and ensure correct reporting of the catch in terms of size, weight, and species. The provision of verifiable catch information and improved evidence of compliance with fisheries regulations will streamline compliance activities for both fisheries and regulators, as well as generating knowledge and data for future conservation, research, and governance activities. Additionally, data provided by the technological innovations under development and testing, can likely contribute to future documentation requirements and expectations from authorities, markets, and consumers.

EVERYFISH will build on and exploit the work done in multiple previous, ongoing, and new projects and further develop key technologies to increase their technology readiness level (TRL). In total, EVERYFISH will develop 10 products and apps for automatic catch recording and reporting, as well as guidelines for implementation and integration of EVERYFISH technologies in commercial fisheries in Europe to optimize improve automatic data collection, provide documentation on fisheries activities and the environmental footprint, evidence of compliance with fishery regulations, and reduce the ecological impact of the sector on the marine environment (Figure 1).

The methods and technologies developed in EVERYFISH will be ready for implementation in commercial fisheries. We assess their TRL in terms of the maturity of the underlying technologies in a fisheries context as several of them, e.g. AI, are already quite mature and used extensively in other sectors but still immature and relatively little used in fisheries management. All the products and apps developed in EVERYFISH are useful as standalone systems to provide automatic catch registration on vessels and by fishers that use them. However, their greatest potential will be realised when the data is standardized and automatically transmitted via a distributed ledger, to be used by stock assessors, fisheries monitoring and management agencies, certification companies, and others. For the fishery industry, data provided by the products and apps developed in the projects holds great potential to be utilized for e.g. marketing purposes to document sustainability, compliance, and traceability.

Figure 1: The conceptual structure of EVERYFISH HEU.

1.2. Role of the deliverable

This is the deliverable of task 5.6, Science - Policy - Industry workshop series in Work package 5.

We will bring together stakeholders representing scientists, policymakers, MCS managers and the fishery industry, creating a multidisciplinary competence network. In total, three workshops will be hosted; the first will include stakeholders representing policy makers and MCS managers, the second will broaden the network, including stakeholders representing science and research, while the final will include stakeholders representing the fishery industry as well. The workshops will address how and why current MCS management compliance strategies could and should be improved, utilizing new and emerging technology being developed, to help end IUU fishing. Other aspects that will be debated throughout the workshops will include, but not be restricted to, routes for implementation and integration of new technology into MCS compliance regulations, minimum requirements needed to be met by technological solutions prior to implementation, data quality and governance, data ownership and how solutions can be utilized in a beneficial way by all stakeholders. Another aspect that will be considered during this work is the socio-economic impact implementation of an AI and technology based MCS management will have on the affected stakeholders in the region. By inviting stakeholders from both science, policy and the industry, the workshops aim to take a holistic approach by identifying conflicts of interests as well as converging interests related to the matter.

Though the aim of the task had originally been to facilitate three workshops, but in the end we chose to increase this to eight. This was because it was decided with partners in case areas that the workshops with the fishers would give better results if held in their native languages. This gave us more depth and understanding and was considered a substantial enhancement compared to the original plan.

1.3. Structure of this document

This document is structured as follows:

- Background
- Methods
- Results
- Concluding remarks.

1.4. Relationship with other deliverables

The Investigation and mapping of stakeholder opinions to the matter of implementation of automated catch registration on board fishing vessels, will serve as the foundation for D5.5. In D5.5, a road map and suggested best practice guidelines for Implementation of automated catch registration technology on board fishing vessels will be prepared with basis in the findings In D 5.4

Table 1: Deliverables that relate to D5.4.

Deliverable no.	Deliverable name	Month due	Partner responsible
D 5.5	Best practice guidelines	30	NDF

1.5. Contributors

The following partners have contributed to this deliverable:

- The Directorate of Fisheries
- SINTEF Ocean
- Çukurova University
- AZTI-Tecnalia
- DTU Aqua

2. Background

Fisheries remains a vital source of protein and income for countries worldwide (FAO, 2022) . However, the increasing efficiency of global fishing fleets puts fish stocks under significant pressure, with an estimated one-third of fishing stocks being overexploited (FAO, 2024). This exploitation has raised concern about illegal, unreported, and unregulated (IUU) fishing (Caro et al., 2022, Jaureguiberry et al., 2022).

IUU-fishing can provide short term benefits for those engaged in illegal practices (Standal and Hersoug, 2023). Under the current situation, the existing monitor, control and surveillance (MCS) efforts struggle to ensure compliance to the applicable regulations (NOU 2019:21). Deploying inspectors on every vessel is economically Impractical necessitating alternative measures.

One potential solution is the development and implementation of automated catch registration technologies on-board fishing vessels. For this approach to succeed, it requires support from governing entities and willingness from fishers to test and integrate such systems into their daily operations. Fishers' acceptance is influenced by their perception of the fairness, meaningfulness and compatibility of new technologies and regulations with their traditional practices and patterns (Mangi et al., 2015, Raakjær Nielsen and Matiesen, 2003).

Support from fishers is crucial, as the necessary technologies for automatic catch registration involve installing and testing equipment on their vessels. These technologies could include cameras, sensors, scanners, IoT-devices, or similar tools, aiming to limit the need for physical observers and manual catch reporting. Emerging technologies, such as machine vision and artificial intelligence, can enhance the mentioned technologies, providing unbiased collection and distribution of high-resolution data, improving MCS beyond the use of cameras for mere monitoring of fishing operations.

This study aims to investigate the perceptions of various stakeholders, including fishers, MCS-managers, and scientist, regarding development and implementation of catch registration technologies on-board fishing vessels. To achieve this, a series of workshops has been conducted across Europe, with a particular focus on the perspectives of fishers from different nations.

3. Methods

In this study, several participatory workshops were organized across Europe, using a stakeholder framework to gather expert knowledge from stakeholders representing the fishery industry, scientists, and fishery management with expertise in MCS. The workshops aimed to explore diverse perspectives on enabling the successful implementation of automated catch registration within European fisheries. Participants were selected based on their profession and direct involvement in issues related to catch registration, possessing expert knowledge and informed opinions on the matter. This included, but were not limited to, economic, regulatory, social, and ecological considerations when developing

recommendations and a roadmap for future management strategies and the uptake of new technologies in the fisheries industry. Most participants were invited based on the snowball method (Biernacki and Waldorf, 1981).

The workshops were structured around three pillars: knowledge sharing, problem-solving and networking. One of the most important aspects of these workshops was to gather relevant stakeholders to share their expertise, experience, and knowledge, and to raise awareness and discuss various aspects of the topic at hand. The next step involved peer-to-peer brainstorming to identify potential solutions, alternatives, and concerns. Finally, the workshops served as great arenas for networking, where the participants engaged in interactive exercises to find creative solutions together. This approach also served the purpose of putting the subject on the agenda of the stakeholders and encouraged them to start considering how the debated topic might impact their future.

Prior to the first workshop, an internal workshop with the core research team was conducted to outline a research question for the upcoming events and identify relevant drivers that could be used as conversation starters during the participatory workshops. This method has been used in several previous studies (Tiller et al., 2016, Tiller and Richards, 2018, Tiller and Richards, 2015). During the internal workshop of core research team, a root cause analysis was conducted, assessing questions such as "What is the problem, and what do we want to achieve?", "Which measures are relevant achieve the desired results?", "Which questions of principle do the suggested measures raise?", "What will be the positive and negative effects of the suggested measures, how long will the effect persist, and who will be affected?", "Which measures are recommended and why?" and "What are the prerequisites for a successful implementation?" (FINANSDEPARTEMENTET, 2024).

Based on the nature of the EVERYFISH project, discussion related to the mentioned root-cause analysis converted to the following research question:

"What will enable the implementation of automated catch registration on board European fishing vessels?"

This question, or a version of this, was used as the research question in all consecutive workshops.

Further discussion led to the identification of seven neutral drivers, which could increase or decrease as individual units. The drivers were:

- Access to areas
- Climate change
- Market
- Quality of Life
- Regulations
- Research
- Technology

The workshops applied a conceptual mapping methodology based on system thinking (Ford, 2019), which involves developing a conceptual map representing a given system as perceived by the participants. This included perceived concepts and variables related to the implementation of automated catch registration on-board European fishing vessels and how these connect. The method is stakeholder-driven and facilitates co-production of knowledge by participants engaging in discussion and sharing their perspectives and experiences. As the discussion proceeds, the facilitator continuously creates a mental map by drawing on a whiteboard for everyone to see and comment on. The seven drivers are used as conversation starters, with the facilitator asking open questions, such as "will fishers' quality of life be impacted by implementation of automatic catch registration on board fishing vessels?". Although the drivers were meant to be conversation starters, stakeholders were encouraged to bring up any topics.

In total, eight separate workshops were arranged between December 2023 and December 2024. The stakeholders represented in the workshops were roughly be divided into three groups: the fishery industry, scientists, and managers. The fishery Industry group consisted mainly of fishers from various fisheries, recreational fishers, and representatives from fishers' organizations. The scientist group included representatives from research institutes covering a wide range of scientific professions, including fishery science, engineering disciplines, and social science. Finally, the manager group consisted mainly of managers with expertise in MCS-management, both at department and directorate levels. Five workshops targeting the fishery industry stakeholders were hosted in four different countries: Norway, Denmark, Spain (two), and Turkey. Additionally, one workshop with managers (divided into two rooms) and one workshop with scientists were hosted in Norway

Table 2: List of completed workshops.

Time	Location	Participants (n)	Stakeholders	Nationalities
December 2023	Tromsø, Norway	20	Professional fishers Fisher interest organizations Sales organizations	Norwegian
February 2024	Bilbao, Spain	10	Tropical Tuna fishers	Spanish
February 2024	Bilbao, Spain	12	Recreational fishers	Spanish

March 2024	Tromsø, Norway	24 (split: 13:11)	MCS managers Department employees Fisheries scientists	Norwegian Danish UK Faroes Icelandic Greenlandic Canadian
June 2024	Adana, Türkiye	16	Professional fishers Coast guard official Port authority staff Ministry employees	Turkish
June 2024	Hirtshals, Denmark	11	Professional fishers Vessel owners Fisheries consultants Observers Fishing association representatives	Danish
October 2024	Bergen, Norway	12	Scientists MCS managers	Norwegian UK

Prior to the workshops, the participating stakeholders were asked to provide written consent to participate in the workshop and indicate if they were comfortable with the session being recorded. Workshops were only recorded if all participants consented; otherwise, sessions were summarized by research group personnel. All workshops were recorded except the two organized in Spain. Recordings were later transcribed, anonymised, and analysed. The co-created mental maps from the workshops, were processed and "refined" by merging concurrent subjects. Finally, the transcripts, where available, were analysed to highlight the opinions of the participating stakeholders.

4. Results

The series of workshop provided valuable input and feedback both fishers, management, and scientists across Europe, highlighting their perceptions, opinions and considerations for implementing automated catch registration on-board European fishing vessels as part of MCS-management.

The concern related to costs was raised multiple times, with one fisher stating:

"It will cost an enormous amount to Implement this on every small fishing vessel that has a quota. And, if this is extended to the recreational fishers, just think about the bureaucracy it would create."

Costs were perceived as the decisive factor, especially for the smaller vessels with smaller quotas and profit margins. Additionally, several participants felt that the study should focus on implementing such technologies at landing sites instead of, or in addition to, on-board systems.

Another concern that was frequently mentioned was the feeling of being criminalized and increased surveillance over the years. One participant noted:

"We are the most monitored sector today; from the moment you leave your bed at home until you are back home."

This statement referred to the current mandatory electronic reporting systems, including position reporting (VMS, mandatory for vessels above 10 meters) and catch and activity reporting (ERS, mandatory for vessels above 11 meters) (Fiskeridirektoratet, 2024). The workshop was held shortly after the implementation of mandatory VMS and ERS for vessels between 11 and 15 meters in Norway, leading to a high focus on the topic. The catch activity is currently manually reported by fishers at sea once every 24 hours in an approved reporting system if they are engaged in active fishing. The catch activity report (DCA) includes total amount of catch in round weight per species.

There was also a belief that the initial research question referred to on technological solution for all vessels, regardless of size or fishing gear. Once moderators explained that multiple systems were being developed, adapted for different vessels, and that these systems could potentially replace current ERS rather than add to them, several participants became increasingly positive. One fisher stated:

"I believe It could be one step in the right direction to remove the catch logbook which only base its numbers on qualified guesses. To implement a technology such as this, given it doesn't cost anything, we are being served on a silver platter. [...] a camera that can count, measure and weigh fish."

Another fisher added:

"As long as I don't have to guess what's in the room [storage of the fish on the vessel], I am very happy".

The fishers acknowledge that the current system could be improved with new technology. However, increased cost remained a primary concern. This concern could be mitigated if the technology also improved traceability, potentially leading to higher payment per kilo fish sold, provided the market is willing to pay for the documentation. This was recognized by the fishers, making the implementation more appealing if the market supports it.

Another heavily debated concern, was the legal certainty of the fishers if automated catch registration technologies were implemented, and potential consequences of system malfunctions or user errors. However, the use of such systems is also seen as an opportunity. If the systems accurately measure the catch and the fishers follow guidelines or regulations, their legal certainty could increase. This was welcomed by some of the participants who currently feel insecure about under- or overestimating the size of their catches in the ERS reporting, which could lead to Infringement fees.

The need for a "level playing field" was also emphasized. If automated catch registration is implemented on fishing vessels, similar technologies should be implemented on landing facilities and other relevant points in the value chain. It was also stressed that if this becomes mandatory for Norwegian vessels, it should also be mandatory for international vessels operating on the same fishing grounds to prevent competitive disadvantages.

Finally, the importance of early involvement of the fishing industry in the development was clearly outlined. Early involvement is essential for successful development and implementation, helping build trust, address concerns, and improve system design. User-friendliness was also highlighted as an important feature.

Key findings:

- Concerns about increased costs, especially for smaller vessels.
- Early involvement of the fishery industry is essential for successful implementation.
- The technology should be reliable, well-tested and user-friendly.
- One size will not fit all vessel sizes and fishing gears.
- The juridical responsibility during use needs to be investigated.
- A level playing field nationally and internationally needs to be emphasized.
- Similar technologies should be implemented at landing sites.
- If implemented, such data should be used to enhance traceability if this can increase the value of the catch.
- If implemented, data should be used for real-time management.

4.1.2. Bilbao, Spain, February 2024

In the two workshops held in Bilbao, Spain, the participants did not consent to recording the meetings, so no transcripts were available for thorough analysis. However, summaries of the findings from each workshop were developed, along with simplified conceptual maps visualizing the findings (Figures 3 and 4). The research question used during the workshop was:

"What will the implementation of automatic recording on board fishing vessels allow?"

The first workshop targeted recreational fishers and was attended by 12 participants. Some were familiar with using technology for automatic recording of catches during competitions, where results were shared among users, highlighting rankings, pictures of catches, etc. The attendees believed such technologies should be user friendly, used in a comfortable environment, and accompanied by training. They consider it appropriate to use this type of technology for scientific and management purposes, while maintaining data privacy, guaranteeing the veracity of the data, and ensuring compliance was seen as important. Sharing this information could positively impact the reputation of recreational fisheries. They also proposed that these tools should provide information on regulatory updates, species and seasonal catch distributions, and emergency tools for security.

Figure 3: Simplified conceptual map, visualizing the findings from the Bilbao workshop with recreational fishers.

In the second workshop, 10 representatives from the purse seine fisheries in Spain attended. Key inputs centred around fisheries regulation and management, research, technologies, and the market. Participants emphasized the need to improve methods for weight and size estimation and to refine technologies for identifying tuna species, as it is difficult to discriminate between certain tuna species at certain ages. Accurate weight estimation influences profits, customer satisfaction, and quota management. Associating a

sustainability certification label with the final product could help promote these technologies, but consumer information and education about such certifications are essential.

Participants suggested that these technologies should also be applied to other fishing gears catching the same species and to non-European fleets, including identification of discarded species as well. Given that fleets with non-European flags operate in the areas where tropical tuna purse seiners fish, these technologies should be enforced and managed by Regional Fisheries Management Organizations (RFMOs). Europe should also close its market to those not complying with European auditing measures. Finally, recordings from the technologies could be used as evidence to avoid sanctions.

Figure 4: Simplified conceptual map, visualizing the findings from the Bilbao workshop with tuna purse seine fishers.

Key findings:

Recreational Fishing:

- Privacy and data security are important.
- The technologies should provide useful information for fishers (e.g., relevant regulations).
- The technologies should be user-friendly, and training should be provided.
- It is regarded as positive if such tools are developed for management and compliance purposes.
- Such technologies should be attractive to use (like a social media platform).

Tropical Tuna Purse Seine Fishing:

- If implemented In the EU, it should become mandatory by non-European countries as well and managed by RFMO's.
- More research and testing are needed to develop such technologies, enhancing systems for better size estimation and species recognition.

"The Idea of full catch documentation, for me at least, means that if the fish are recorded on camera».

Several aspects this were discussed. Participants believed that the systems should be directly linked to the e-log (electronic reporting system) and, if applied on-board vessels, should lead to exemptions from landing obligations if all legal discards were registered. This would be regarded as a significant benefit, especially if the system could automatically record bycatch. However, fishers felt that such a system should primarily be regarded as a tool for them, not just a tool for MCS. Data from the system should be used to report to authorities, provided it is well-tested, documented and trusted by all relevant parties. Formal approval of such systems should apply. A trusted and approved system should lead to juridical security for the fisher. In their opinion, data analysis should be conducted in real time on-board the vessel. One fisher stated:

"When the system is running, and you have artificial Intelligence, the aim must be that the system should be "perfect", so that the data is uploaded from end to end. It should also follow the e-log."

Another fisher added:

"I would like to support what is happening in Kattegat [use of cameras to document fisheries activities], with an AI-system that is running on board, where the fishers could benefit the numbers there and then".

There was a general consensus that using AI to register catch on-board vessels would be the future. This was echoed by another fisher who stated:

"If we're talking about a camera system where it is people [Inspectors] analysing the data following the events [fishing operations], we don't trust this."

This opinion stems from the impact cameras on vessels can have on the quality of life for fishers, who feel monitored and potentially criminalized by authorities. The main concern was that authorities might retroactively impose sanctions several months after a fishing operation, based on video review by inspectors, creating a prolonged period of suspicion. Data protection was also emphasized, with concerns that video and data could be misused against them, whether analysed by AI or human inspectors. Therefore, data protection should be a top priority, ensuring the fishers' data is kept proprietary.

Another thoroughly discussed aspect was the need for regulatory development following technological advances. There was a strong perception that data from these systems should ease regulations, such as technical measures (e.g., fishing gear requirements), improved access to closed or protected areas under certain conditions, landing obligations, and faster opening of areas subject to real-time closure (RTC).

The final major aspect debated during the workshop was the potential impact automated catch registration technologies might have on the market access and prices in the future. Participants were generally

optimistic about certifications becoming increasingly important for fetching a premium price for the fish.

One participant stated:

"I believe that MSC or other types of documentations, in time, will provide a premium price [for the catch]."

The general perception was that automated catch registration would play a role in meeting the increased demand for documentation related to traceability and transparency of value chains. The most optimistic participants expected a premium price for well-documented and certified products in the future, while the more pessimistic ones believed that such documentation would be necessary to maintain current prices.

Key findings:

- Implementation of automated catch registration on board fishing vessels should lead to revised regulations, faster opening of RTC-areas and better access to areas.
- Data ownership, data sharing and GDPR need to be addressed.
- Fishers' quality of life is important, and heavily impacted by surveillance and suspicion.
- Technology being implemented needs to be user-friendly, reliable, and trusted by all stakeholders.
- The systems should be fully automated and analyse data in real time. Data should be automatically linked to the e-log.
- There is a firm opinion that documentation of transparency, traceability and sustainability will become increasingly important for market access in the future.

4.2. Manager workshop, Tromsø, Norway, March 2024

The workshop targeting managers was so large that participants were split into two sessions in separate rooms, relative evenly divided (13:11). This approach led to two co-created conceptual maps (Figures 5 and 6), showcasing the complexity of the number of variables affecting and being affected by the given drivers in both workshops. The drivers that received most attention was "Technology (including research and development)", "Market" and "Regulations». Additionally, it was noted in both workshops that money had a considerable impact on all drivers, especially highlighted in one of the rooms (Figure 5). The following summary addresses the discussions in both workshops combined.

Another aspect highlighted throughout the discussions was the need to demonstrate the benefits of implementing these kinds of technologies for the fishery industry. One manager stated:

"Is it clear to the industry what the benefits are? And one of the things that I think is going to be needed in terms of enabling implementation is trying to demonstrate what those benefits are. That will go a long way to gaining trust in terms of being clear what data [generated] are for, how they will be used, and what the benefits will be".

This showcases the importance of involving all relevant stakeholders, especially the fishery industry, to demonstrate the benefits of using automated catch registration on board vessels. It was also discussed that the utilization and implementation of new technologies in fisheries generally leads to scepticism by several stakeholders, particularly regarding something as unfamiliar as artificial intelligence. Therefore, thorough testing, documentation and involvement from relevant stakeholders will be needed. The need for standardization of data and systems was also highlighted, along with the need to map different stakeholders (e.g. managers, researchers, industry) data needs. Additionally, technology readiness for different sectors of the industry also needs to be considered, along with the need for robust, reliable, user-friendly solutions.

A topic brought to attention during both workshops was the philosophical idea of a system that register all catch that is brought on-board using technology. One manager stated:

"What about an overall philosophy that the aim is to get the catch fully correctly without any kind of involvement of humans? Because humans, they do wrong stuff, they could make mistakes they don't necessarily plan to do, and the tech stuff can, in an ideal world, give us 100 % facts. [...] We should avoid running after the industry, we should set up some kind of tech wall."

The idea of a "tech wall" that forces all catch to go through it was seen positively by many for acquiring documentation related to the actual catch. However, technology readiness and trust in the technology were again discussed as potential obstacles. Additionally, such a system would not necessarily uncover or document discarding or high grading of fish. It was pointed out that if such a system were to be implemented, these issues would need similar focus.

The potential for increased value of the catch based on traceability and transparency was also highlighted as a potential benefit that could be built upon automated catch registration on board vessels. It was noted that several markets value such documentation, which can create higher revenue. However, it was also suggested that while there is an increasing market for traceable and sustainable fish, there is also an increasing demand for protein in general, where this type of information might not necessarily give a premium price. Another aspect pointed out was the potential for creating new markets based on unutilized species, which today are considered low-value bycatch, by utilizing data from automated catch registration technologies.

Like earlier workshops, a level playing field was brought up during these conversations as well. One manager stated:

"[...] If calculating risk among nations is different, it might end up with different tech required so all of this comes down to a level playing fields in similar fleets, similar tech, similar coverage and then everybody probably feels easier about If you're a fisherman."

This was echoed by another manager:

"Yeah, it's easier If you can see your fellow ship from another country Is having the same regulations as you have."

A level playing field was regarded as a highly important topic, with the need for consultations and collaboration for the future development of technology used in MCS management. This development would need to go hand in hand with technological development, adaptation of regulations, and juridical considerations. It was pointed out that political willingness to implement such systems is eventually needed to make this a reality.

Key Findings:

- One size does not fit all. Vessels, fisheries, and technology readiness varies from fishery to fishery and from nation to nation.
- Industry involvement is crucial, and a win-win situation for stakeholders needs to be created.
- Data generated through such technologies holds a big potential for premium payment and can potentially create new markets for unutilized species.
- Technology needs to be user-friendly, well-documented, and well-tested to gain trust among stakeholders. The purpose of the use of technology needs to be addressed (e.g. use in logbooks, science, quota deduction).
- Cost of the systems is a concern, especially for smaller vessels.
- There is a need for harmonization of data and technology standards to create a level playing field.
- Technology to prevent discard and high grading should be addressed.
- Political willingness to implement new technologies must be present.

4.3. Scientist workshop, Bergen, Norway, October 2024

During the workshop with scientists in Bergen, the research question was altered to gain a different perspective. The new question read:

"To what degree did the following variables affect the uptake of new technologies for automated catch registration"

"Two things that drives the development is basically how good your learning algorithms are and how good your data is".

Scientists working with this type of technology emphasized the importance of data collection for training and the need for funding to continue work on standardization of data, data collection, and development of robust learning algorithms. Another important factor to consider is that it is very difficult to get private actors to invest in technology under development, which is likely to provide beneficial services and data in the future. Therefore, incentives and funding for such development need to come from authorities and the public sector, and political will to implement such systems will be crucial.

The discussion continued towards the need for cost-efficient transfer of different types of data from vessels to use data in real time for management, the fishery industry, researchers, and the market. It was also stated that regulations need to develop in conjunction with the technology, and that what is registered on the vessels should match the amount of catch registered when landed, meaning complementary technologies downstream in the value chain.

Another aspect highlighted as important for several stakeholders is the incentivization to share data. It was stated that fishers need to see the benefit of sharing data, for instance, by using the data to reduce the amount of time spent searching for the catch, which saves time and fuel consumption. For marine researchers, high-resolution catch data is beneficial for mapping migration patterns caused by factors such as climate change. They are always interested in using the best available data in their research, especially when conducting stock estimations or giving quota advice.

Finally, the need for regulatory changes was emphasized in conjunction with technological development, along with a clarification of who is juridically responsible when automatic catch recording is implemented if the system fails. The need for international collaboration to create a level playing field and standardization of data and equipment was also emphasized.

Key Findings:

- The technology needs to provide incentives for the fishers to adopt it, such as lower administrative burden.
- The systems need to be well-tested, documented, and trusted.
- Privacy concerns needs to be taken into consideration, together with legal concerns when using such systems.
- The cost of the systems must be sustainable for the industry, while market expectations for sustainability documentation needs to be taken into consideration.
- To develop robust and good technology, sufficient high-quality data is needed.
- Incentives and technology for data sharing are and will be Important.
- International cooperation and harmonization of regulations are considered important.

5. Concluding remarks

The series of workshops conducted across Europe provided valuable insights into the perceptions and considerations of fishers, managers, and scientists regarding the implementation of automated catch registration technologies on fishing vessels. Key findings from these workshops highlight several critical factors for successful implementation:

1. **Cost and Economic Feasibility:** The cost of implementing new technologies is a significant concern, especially for smaller vessels.
2. **Stakeholder Involvement:** Early and continuous involvement of the fishery industry is essential. This helps build trust, address concerns, and improve system design, ensuring that the technology is user-friendly and meets the needs of all stakeholders.
3. **Technology and Data Management:** The technology must be reliable, well-tested, and capable of real-time data analysis. Data ownership, sharing, and protection (GDPR compliance) are crucial considerations. Automated systems should aim to reduce the administrative burden on fishers and enhance data quality for better management and compliance.
4. **Regulatory and Juridical Considerations:** There is a need for regulatory development in tandem with technological advances. Clear guidelines on juridical responsibility and the use of data for real-time management are necessary.
5. **Market and Traceability:** The potential for increased market value through enhanced traceability and sustainability certifications is recognized. However, a level playing field must be established both nationally and internationally to prevent competitive disadvantages.
6. **Privacy and Surveillance:** Privacy concerns, particularly regarding the use of cameras, need to be addressed. Ensuring that surveillance does not negatively impact fishers' quality of life is vital.
7. **International Collaboration:** Harmonization of data and technology standards, along with international cooperation, is essential for creating a consistent and fair regulatory environment.

These findings underscore the importance of a holistic approach that considers economic, social, and regulatory factors to successfully implement automated catch registration technologies in the fisheries industry.

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